

Game-Based Education as a Support Tool in Teaching: A Home Economics Introspection in Focus

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Abstract. This study explored Game-based education as a support tool in teaching Home Economics in the Division of Tagum City, Davao del Norte. There were eight (8) Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers teaching Home Economics subjects who participated in the study. This study made use of a phenomenological approach to extract the ideas from the teacher informants. The participants were purposely selected as representatives from the group of secondary schools in the same division. The virtual in-depth interview and utilization of Google forms were employed to gather information. Using the thematic analysis, the following themes emerged regarding the work experiences of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers in utilizing game-based education as a support tool in teaching Home Economics. These were the following themes that emerged in the study, the active participation and engagement of the students, the application of technical skills, enhanced delivery of the lesson, and supported teaching styles. The challenges they have encountered in utilizing game-based education were the lack of gadgets and devices, difficulty in finding appropriate games and activities, low level computer literacy of teachers and students, limited time for preparation and suitability of the lesson. The insights drawn were the proper selection of games and activities, the willingness of the teachers to learn new skills, and the readily available gadgets and devices in school and in the classroom. With this, school personnels and stakeholders may help hand in hand for the adaptation of the study. Teachers may always be willing to learn and adapt to a more responsive teaching and learning for the benefit of the learners. The study could be adapted for use by other stakeholders such as parents, private schools and even the government. The study could further develop the DepEd's current curriculum or even to craft a new one.

KEY WORDS

1. Game-Based 2. Home Economics 3. Support Tool in Teaching

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1. Introduction

As fast-evolving tech applications, games are more frequently integrated with the standard educational process. It is commonly adopted in educational field, and studies emerged that explored a link between games and learning (Yang et al, 2011). Due to the rapid advancement of technology teachers and policy makers are eager to bring in new technical tools, such as video games, virtual worlds or online games, into the classroom (Gómez, 2014). This is why teachers and students seamlessly incorporate educational games into their daily classroom activities. A

few examples include card games, board games, role playing games, word games, puzzle games, simulation games, video games, etc. when integrated with the teachers. Based on this, the facilitator desires to do this course in a different way rather than making this more of a boring classroom-based course and the intention to include actionable classroom activities that would engage the students and encourage their creativity and imagination. Game-Based Learning is one of the most popular game methods to help students achieve their learning objectives. Especially with the advent of education technology and pupils getting more fast-paced at a younger age. Education is one of the industries that is the most affected by the rapid development of technology. Mobile learning is one such example which is enabled by a cellphone, netbooks and other mobile technology to learn at any time and from any location. 2 Indonesia's Department of Mathematics Education has recognized the importance of integrating game-based learning into mathematics education. The selected junior high school students in Indonesia experience cognitive and emotional improvements from this. It is expected that math teachers and learning designers can develop visual learning resources through the instructional game as a new learning setting for students (Pratama Setyaningrum, 2018). Moreover, game-based learning is mostly contributed by traditional games, but the phenomenon of the upsurge of internet games in the Philippine educational system is hardly known. Acquiring such precepts as global and contingent learning, education and the situational aspect of learning, and transfer of learning that employs usage of troubleshooting capabilities have all facilitated this. Rules and goals drawn from outside that social and community context when playing short games engender a sense of intrinsic motivation, in that players are required and driven to reach these

objectives and goals in a specified timeframe. Like reading, implementing games in the classroom provides teachers with a creative way to teach otherwise unconventional material that will engage students by participating in real-life situations as well (Alviz, 2018). Furthermore, as the traditional educational system is being challenged, technology integration is on the rise. Though we have had multiple chances to blend several technologies into classroom training, we need to understand how proven game-based learning can be blended with the traditional classroom training delivery. Appropriating a new method: In their study in one of Davao City's schools, Boldadora (2018) tried to compare experimental and control groups, where experimental group employed twice as much as a new approach—digital game-based learning—while control group instruction was a traditional one. The study indicates that digital game-based learning improves students' performance in mathematics. In these days fast growing technology such as smart phones, high end computers and improved internet connection across each nation, our educational system must also adopt to these changes and implement it for the benefit of the teachers and learners. The presence of mobile phones, tablets, computers and other devices in the market can also be a new means of introducing new ways of learning in the different institutions. With the help of other stakeholders, the level of education in our country can be improved by contributing its effort in producing these devices for the schools to be used. One great factor in contributing to success in the process of teaching and learning is the skills and the level of understanding of the teacher inside the classroom. Teachers as the facilitator of game-based education needed the necessary support in the implementation of the program.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study is to explore the narratives of the home economics teachers as they utilize game-based education. Furthermore, this study unveiled the realities in terms of the experiences of home economics teachers as they utilize game-based education in enhancing their 4 proficiency in teaching. The challenges encountered by the teachers as they utilized the game-based education in teaching home economics and lastly, this study provides a good avenue in identifying the insights coming from the home economics teachers-based form their narratives.

1.2. Research Questions—This research investigated the encounters of Tagum City Division Home Economics Teachers working in Davao del Norte Province. The research aims to answer specific questions regarding Home Economics teacher experiences in Tagum City Division of Davao del Norte Province.

- (1) Home Economics Teachers demonstrate different experiences when incorporating game-based approaches to improving their instructional practices.
- (2) Home economics educators face which problems when they apply game-based education to their subject instruction?
- (3) What valuable information emerges from the combination of home economics teacher experience with their game-based education struggles?

1.3. Definition of Terms—In an effort to augment this analysis, the following concepts are operationally defined. Education through games. Some game concepts are borrowed and applied to real-world situations in an effort to engage consumers (Trybus, 2015). The specific goal is to develop educational exercises that can guide users towards a final goal, while slowly but gradually introducing topics. Economics of the home. This reflects the specific domain where game-based learning will serve as an aiding mechanism. Support Tool. Any tools, programs, or other resources designed to help the teacher in carrying out their instructional strategies and achieve a particular goal. This could have varied accordingly depending on the teacher's technical wizardry with the technology.

1.4. Significant of the Study—This research focuses on two groups of beneficiaries comprising school administrators and the selected group of home economics teachers in Hanoi. Department of Education Staff. Results of this study would be particularly beneficial in the Tagum City Division since they would provide a clearer 5 understanding of how game-based learning can be an aid for home economics teachers teaching in their respective schools. Administrators of schools. Not only does it provide a plausible account of why we don't see more real game integration in education (games simply require a much heftier investment of time and resources and there are few standards to follow to help educators in the complex process of integrating games into formal learning environments), it generates some meaningful ideas for how games-based education can bridge the knowledge gap. Teachers of home economics. This study aims to raise awareness and provide information on existing game-based educational tools that can be used to improve the teaching and learning process in the different schools in Tagum City Division. Students of home economics. Students who possess some technological proficiency, namely with regards to gaming-based learning, may be particularly

drawn to the subject. Researchers of the Future. Data that may be relevant to game-based education as a support tool for home economics teachers, or in another field and location, may

1.5. Theoretical Lens—John Dewey (1859-1952) believed learning should activate students through multiple experiential activities as per his Social Activist Theory. The educational process of social learning requires active participation (Conner 2011). 19 Educators frequently use games (board games, card games, and roleplaying games) in their classrooms but their main objective always served learning rather than entertaining students. The educational application of games proved beneficial for teachers who needed them to explain learning concepts or reinforce already acquired knowledge in the classroom. Using games in educational settings helps to simplify matters according to Van Ments (1999). The Information Age challenges teachers to embrace change. Computer literacy is an essential skill requirement for students in the modern world and teachers must accept and welcome this (Murchu Freeman, 2003). Piaget’s (1936) theory of cognitive development explains how a child constructs a mental model of the world. Piaget (1936) composed four cognitive development stages concerning child development from birth to adulthood: sensorimotor; pre-operational; concrete operational; and formal operational. Papila and Olds (1996) believed learners acquire information based on maturity, knowledge, environment, and ability during each developmental stage (as cited in Ojose, 2008). In 1962, Piaget described play as being integral to, and evolving with, children’s stages of cognitive development (Plass et al., 2015). Plass et al. (2015) noted that play, the essential activity in games, is considered as a critical element in human development. Educators can benefit from understanding their students’ devel-

be helpful to future researchers who wish to investigate the use of game-based education as a support tool for home economics teachers or in another field and location.

opmental stage and should attempt to establish their students’ cognitive levels to alter their pedagogical practices (Ojose, 2008). 20 The principles of constructivism consist of attributes from Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky. According to Piaget’s perspective of constructivism, “people learn through active exploration and learning occurs when the learner’s exploration uncovers an inconsistency between their current knowledge representation and their experience” (Obikwelu Read, 2012). Furthermore, Vygotsky believed learning transpires within a social environment, and the interaction amongst learners and their peers is a crucial component of the learning process (Obikwelu Read, 2012). Driscoll (2000) asserted that the constructivist theory assumes that knowledge is constructed by learners as they attempt to make sense of their experiences. Meaning, learners are active organisms seeking meaning (Driscoll, 2000) This study is anchored on the Instructional Theory by Bruner (1966) which states that, instruction should address four major aspects: (1) predisposition towards learning, (2) the ways in which a body of knowledge can be structured so that it can be most readily grasped by the learner, (3) the most effective sequences in which to present material, and (4) the nature and pacing of rewards and punishments. Because the best techniques for structuring knowledge should be simplified, generate new hypotheses, and enable more handling of information. Instruction should be focused on the experiences and situations that ready the student to learn (readiness), structured such that comprehension is facilitated (spiral organization), and designed to either supplement (tie in/use what they already know) and/or extend (beyond the

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

information give). Teaching wise, the teacher should strive to encourage students to learn concepts independently. Active dialogue (Socratic learning) between the teacher and the learner. It is the instructor's responsibility to take material to be learnt and translate it to something that the learner can work with at their current level of understanding. The curriculum should be organized in a spiral nature, enabling learners to build upon what they already know. James Finn (1953) concluded on the theory for Instructional Technology that in education technology is more than an intervention, more than a machine, since it is the process, system, management and control mechanism both human and non-human resources, and by at large, the attitudes of looking at problems as to their interest and difficulty

of resolving them. This theory implies that with the use of technology, which relates to an appropriate instructional design, the teacher will be ready to all teaching activities he/she will have in the classroom and therefore, the students' academic performance will be enhanced. Moreover, this study was supported by the principle of good teaching by John Dewey (1931) which stated that good teaching requires a rich environment of instructional materials and devices. A good teaching approach becomes effective when additional teaching materials enhance the learning method selected. The synthesis of various methods creates an effective learning method according to accepted standards. The best learning occurs through the activation of multiple senses during the learning process.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research design to be used, the role of the researcher, the participants in the study, how data will be collected, the type of data analysis applied, the study's trustworthiness, and ethical considerations. The three most popular qualitative design strategies include participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each design is tailored for extracting a particular type of data. So, one can learn about naturally occurring behaviors as they play out in their natural settings through participant observation. In-depth interviews (IDI) are the most effective way to understand a person's history, viewpoint, and experiences, especially when major concerns are in the inquiry (IQ). These focus groups aid in producing broad summaries of topics important to the cultural groups or subgroups represented, as well as in understanding any cultural norms associated with that designated group. "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" is one of the questions that Patton, M. (2002) identified as phenomenology. This concept was a good fit for the research's objective, which was to examine the varying gender preferences of secondary school heads. Giorgi (2007) advised researchers to be ready for an examination that is more comprehensive and in-depth than the description provided suggested. Information is just the top of the iceberg, he suggested.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework utilized to accumulate, analyze and translate the information collected in a particular field of study. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are explained below. Stanage (2017) traces 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model for example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm is an action of submitting to a view (Stanage 2017). This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000) who defend a research paradigm a "basic set of belief that guide action", dealing with first principles, "ultimate" or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains on how the issue relates to the nature of reality. Concurring to Creswell (2013) reality could be subjective and multiple as seen by participants of the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for subjective analyst. Reality is built by people included in the research situation. Thus, multiple realists exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, I depended on voices and interpretations of the participants through wide cites, themes that reflected their words and given confirmations of assorted perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to create and develop for the commonality and discreteness of reactions.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—Do not confuse method with methodology. Whereas methodology is a creative and adaptive manner of exploring and knowing problems and the subject matter (Gerodias, 2013) methodology is more about detailed data and process. This study will explore the digital game-based strategy as a learning tool for home economic teachers in Tagum City. Qualitative research was conducted since the researcher wanted to help home economics teachers in Tagum City's Division through game-based learning. The necessity of the phenomenon in gameplay that supports the home economics teacher to improve

the teaching-learning process in the classroom was designed to fulfill this need. There are two assumptions that underlie phenomenological in-

quiry. The first is that the meeting may be important.

2.3. Design and Procedure—Qualitative research carried out this study through phenomenological methods. First-hand experiencers of events and circumstances will undergo interview procedures as part of the research design. The research team read the information multiple times to collect similar phrases and

themes that led to the generation of meaningful clusters (Creswell, 2013). The holistic meaning about the event or situation and interactions was derived by the researcher during this process leading to deeper knowledge about the phenomenon. Lin (2017) explains this qualitative research design fits the study aims to explore the essence of designated phenomena.

2.4. Research Participants—There were ten (10) informants in this research. Purposive Sampling Chosen Informant Derived Five (5) Secondary Schools from Tagum City Division—Tagum City National Comprehensive High School, Tagum City National High School, La Filipina National High School, Tagum City National Trade School, and Laureta National High School All participants in this study were home economics teachers who were very knowledgeable about the topic and incorporated game-based learning into the teaching and learning process. The replying is at least five to 10 years of home economics. Qualitative research often has a smaller sample size when compared to quantitative research. Qualitative samples need not be, and should not be, large but should be large enough to obtain comment on most attitudes. SENSORY SATURATION: All or nearly all senses will be impacted. Just as with the world of seven above, too many study participants also lead to saturation: it means only so much richness, information, awareness of a consequence, is left to be gained by adding one more participant, it's worth zero. Carlsen Glentos (2011) suggested that qualitative researchers lack transparency in terms of sample sizes and their rationales.

2.5. Ethical Consideration—Qualitative research interacts with participants at various points in the study even before and after data collection and therefore may yield ethical dilemmas between researchers and participants due to the nature of qualitative research. Hence, it is extremely important to lay down some ethical principles in this domain. The primary ethical criterion for any study should ideally be scientific logicalness. This research must be appropriately prepared and presented by researchers who have the requisite supervision and training. It should—if that is, there are pronounced benefits (Richards Schwartz, 2012). In addition, qualitative researchers must specify at the development what data will be collected and what it would be used for (Sanjari, 2014). He also noted 42 that informed consent is required for any research that makes use of identifiable individuals but is not required in cases where an ethics committee determines that this is not possible or when it is deemed that the benefits of the study outweigh the dangers. At minimum, an interview study should expect participants to provide written informed consent, including verbally and in writing informing them about the aim and scope of study, type of questions parenthetical likely to be asked, anonymization procedure, use of the results, and how far (or not) their statements

would be incorporated into reports. Participants should also have time to reflect on their participation and ask any questions they have of the researcher. Some of these include the type of study, the degree of involvement of the subjects, the identity of the researcher, the purpose of the

study, and how the findings will be shared and used. Likewise, this study was also submitted for approval and validation to the ethics committee of the graduate school of Rizal Memorial College.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher who conducted this study worked on revealing the emotional and cognitive states of research participants. The research strategy required informants to share points which might hold personal significance to their lives. Researchers might find variability in the difficulty level of participants to recall experiences de-

pending on whether these events happen within the present or occurred in the past. The process of data collection brings a primary obligation for researchers to protect participants along with their gathered information. The research methods for safeguarding participants need clear explanations to research participants and must receive ethical board approval prior to starting the study.

2.7. Data Collection—As Creswell (2013) notes: The important steps in this process include finding people or locations to study and gaining access to them, building relationships with participants so that they ultimately will provide data that is useful. The selection of a technique for the intentional sampling of individuals or places is a step in the process that is intimately related to the others. After deciding the places or subjects, the best possible way to gather data must be determined. Written

procedures or protocols, such as observational or interview protocols, are developed by the researcher to record this type of data. The researcher also has to anticipate data-collecting issues, called field issues, which could range from not enough data, needing to expedite the field or site, or being the cause of information loss, among others. Finally, as with analysis, the qualitative researcher must decide how to store data to ensure that it remains accessible whilst protected from loss or damage.

2.8. Data Analysis—All data collected for this study was heavily reviewed and closely analyzed. To begin, the researcher discussed her own relationship with the topic being studied. To begin with, the researcher described how she personally experienced the phenomenon. So, to keep the participants in the center of focus of the research, the researcher is trying to set aside their own experience. You create a list of important statements, and then you look at how people feel about the subject, then you rank these claims as equally important, and you try to come up with a list of statements that is not repeated or do not overlap. The bolded declara-

tions were afterward attributed by the researcher to “meaning units,” or themes (larger informational units). The researcher wrote a description of “what” the study participants experienced with the event. The scientist subsequently wrote an article describing “how” the encounter unfolded. This was called structural description, and the analyst considers the context and situations of phenomena. Eventually, the researcher integrated this description of structure with a description of texture to arrive at a composite description of the phenomena. This paragraph, the last piece of a phenomenological investigation into the “essence” of the experience/embed-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study)

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—Braun and Clark (2006) define two types of qualitative data analysis techniques. Methods in the first group include grounded theory, discourse analysis (DA), and narrative analysis (NA). Each of these approaches is informed by an epistemological or theoretical position but has relatively little flexibility in how to apply them within their frameworks. Other approaches, including conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA), are embed-

ded in a wide-ranging theoretical framework, meaning that they can be employed in a range of ways within those frameworks. The second type of methods are non-theory- or epistemology-dependent: These methods are highly versatile and can be used with a broad range of theoretical and epistemological frameworks. Braun and Clark (2006) note that, while "theoretical freedom" makes thematic analysis a very useful research technique, "it can also produce complex and detailed accounts of data."

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Study rigor or trustworthiness is the degree of confidence in data, interpretation, and procedures used to ensure that a study is of high quality (Pilot Beck, 2014). Trustworthiness is impor-

tant for credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability.: In qualitative research, it is paramount to ensure trustworthiness since the researcher's method is responsible for the findings and conclusions of the study. Credibility is

critical when determining the value of a research study. Because qualitative research qualities necessitate truthfulness in all data and information. A study that is reliable is one that's worthy to be read, and shared, and shared. Credibility is the extent to which the qualitative researcher believes that the findings of the study are true. The study's researcher said that doing everything

straight is key to making something meaningful. Researcher is administratively sound, with no bad track record, that compromises their integrity. Internal consistency is to the concept of credibility, "the core issue is how we demonstrate, and convince others of, rigor in the research process," (Lincoln Guba, 2000).

3. Results and Discussion

The research questions and participant-based responses formed the focus of this study section. People from the Tagum City education sector in Davao del Norte explained their utilization of games as educational teaching tools.

3.1. Experiences of Home Economics Teachers in Utilizing Game-based Education in Enhancing Proficiency in Teaching—This qualitative research is intended to unravel the experiences of the teachers as they utilized game-based education in enhancing the proficiency of home economics teacher during the last quarter of the school year 2021-2022.

3.1.1. Active participation and engagement of the students—One key in a successful classroom lesson was when you observed the active participation and maximum engagement of the students in the class discussion and activities. With the help of multimedia instructions and gamified activities, the students were provided with different materials and tools that are fun, exciting and lively. Considering that our lesson must be a learner-centered, the delivery of the lesson became easy and lively. Thus, it really supported the teacher in the delivery of the lesson. Incorporating games into the classroom to implement and use must also bring educators a wide range of important roles. It was also seen that the various skills needed for carrying out these tasks effectively included a wide range of subjects' expertise, knowledge of video games, technical know-how and, of course, a good understanding of pedagogy. What this means is this: before designing a game-based

learning curriculum, the instructor will have to determine the current state of his learning environment. That will involve looking at things like what sort of organization is behind and supporting one's learning, whether such hardware and software are available, and if other resources or obstacles exist. Teachers could use digital game-based learning to help students acquire abilities. According to Serrano (2019), when digital game-based learning blends important game design features (collaboration, choice, feedback) and instructional design, for example, there is typically a beneficial impact on student engagement. "In essence, what we mean by digital game-based learning is educational content or learning theory built into computer or video games in the hope of making learners enthusiastic learners" was how Coffey (2017) defined it as another sentence.

3.1.2. Application of technical skills—As a teacher in implementing game-based education in the class is, one should have the necessary skills before using it to have good results. The teachers already have the skills but updating and 46 relearning are still necessary. They need to review the skills they have, the environment they can use and the available resources they can incorporate. The teacher's development of the lesson depends on the ability and

skills he/she has. Lack of adequate training and learning resources can cause ineffectiveness of the lesson. These challenges on the part of the teacher can be addressed through proper support, training and acquiring the necessary skills in utilization of this kind of education. In the 21st century, these skills are a must for the teachers to enable them to manipulate and develop lessons that are suitable for the learners. These skills are essential in today's school systems as more tasks are completed using computer technologies. For a teacher to be recognized as good, Kochhar (2004) stated that he/she must possess these characteristics: identifies individual variances among learners; dynamic; imaginative; logical; dares learners to learn; simplifies and stimulate learning etc. Again, for effective teaching, he proposed that the teacher must teach from; known to the unknown, simple to the complex, whole to part, concrete to abstract, analysis to synthesis and many more. Teacher indulges in technology and can be able to manipulate any applications that may be used in instruction is called computer literate. This skill enables the teacher to manipulate the computer in a better way for the development of the lesson. There are two distinct components to computer literacy, these are awareness and competence. Awareness "requires an individual to have knowledge of how computers affect his/her daily life or society as a whole", and competence "requires an individual to demonstrate a hands-on proficiency with a software application" (Jenkins, 2008).

3.1.3. Enhanced delivery of the lessons—Game-based education is structured to integrate games into the subject matter in order to increase the students' ability to acquire knowledge and promote engagement, collaboration, problem solving and motivate them to learn. Students nowadays are more familiar with games especially online games, because of the readily available application inside their own smartphone. Game-based education offers inter-

active delivery from the students to the media they used or to the teachers giving the instructions. In the study conducted by Hamari et al. (2015), it showed that engagement in the game has a clear positive effect on learning, however, it did not have the effect on learning directly but increased engagement in the games. Both the challenge of the game and being skilled in the game had a positive effect on both being engaged and immersed in the game. The challenge in the game was an especially strong predictor of learning outcomes. In addition to that, collaboration and cooperative learning in digital game-based design, as well as instructional design, were found to be successful in increasing student engagement (De Freitas, 2018). Game-based education uses game in learning for instance puzzles and bingo games that are entrenched into a lesson. Abdussalim (2008) asserted that it is a substantial feature in the teaching and learning process. Game elements like leader boards, trophies, point systems, badges and others are used. Findlay (2016) opined that Game-based learning is an experience which requires the use of game mechanics to instill a particular skill or attain a precise learning result. It takes the main content and goals and makes it fun. In a GBL learning situation, students study fresh ideas and also practice skills in a situation devoid of risk. Student's development in the game is directly linked with their ability to comprehend the subject matter being taught. It also has a substantial effect on recalling rates.

3.1.4. Supported teaching styles—Game-based education has become a great opportunity for both the learners and the teachers. It fosters the teacher on how he/she facilitates the lesson and encourages self-learning through guided interaction, feedback and how the activity flows in the lesson. Students can easily perform the task and excited to accomplish it. Games in the lesson motivates the learners to think fast and correctly. Accompanied with the challenges in the lesson brought out by the games, stu-

Fig. 3. The Experience of Home Economics Teachers in Utilizing Game-Based Education in Enhancing Proficiency in Teaching Home Economics.

dents activate their higher order thinking skills like comprehending the instructions, evaluating the game and applying what they learned. Educators who have useful competence will seriously produce a creative and easy-to-understand learning media to help students face learning challenges (Baumert et al., 2020; Fauth et al., 2019). Smith Blake (2005) took a standby saying teaching includes the drill of assisting learning rather than simply transmitting knowledge to the learners. In a study conducted by Yu et al. (2014) in mainland China it showed that the participants in a Computer Game Based In-

struction obtained a significantly greater learning achievement than those who didn't participate. Participants were significantly more motivated but there were no significant differences in learning achievement between boys and girls. This shows that when it comes to application and instruction. It is difficult for the teacher to switch between different teaching styles and approaches from time to time. Furthermore, different games may have different influences upon education and one game may be effective in one subject while the other may not.

3.2. Challenges Encountered by Home Economics Teachers in Utilizing Game-based Education—Game-based education is another way of delivering the lesson, but it also brings new challenges to the teachers utilizing it. This involves the selection of suitable games and activities that can be used and adapted to the

desired outcome of the teachers. With the different tasks of the teachers inside the school, time is the most challenging part of the preparation. This also adds the burden to teachers in spending time learning the way of the game and its process and thinking how we can take advantage of the features of the game in our lesson.

Based on the accounts of the home economics teachers in utilizing game-based education in teaching home economics, some insights were drawn to further improve the management of teachers in employing game-based education in the lesson for further improvement based on the challenges they have encountered.

3.2.1. Difficulty in finding appropriate games and activities—Teachers' selection and preparation of the game-based education is a great factor in the success of the lesson. This involves planning and providing students with the opportunity to develop the skills they need to accomplish the activity. In addition to that, students' knowledge and ideas about the different games must be considered in order to align learning activities with what the learners can do. With the different games present on the internet, appropriateness in using the game and aligning the objective of the games to the objective of the lesson must be considered. This process consumes time and effort for the teachers before selecting the best game for the lesson discussion or activity. Most of the participants were united in telling the researcher that there is a need to select games and activities that are easy to understand by the students and easy to access by the teachers. It also emphasizes on the suitability of the games and activities used to the lesson and the topic the teacher needs to deliver for the class. The Philippine education sector mainly employs traditional games for game-based learning while online games have not been extensively studied for educational purposes. The learning tenets of personalized and situated learning together with critical and active learning and transfer of learning fostered approaches to problem solving. Games maintain specific regulations which force users to achieve targets before time expires while simultaneously sustaining internal drive. Marklund Taylor (2014) revealed in their study that teachers need to take on a wide variety of important roles when integrating and using games in their

educational environment. The skill sets needed to perform the roles well were also found to be quite diverse as they involved technological know-how, gaming literacy, subject matter expertise, and naturally a strong pedagogical foundation. In choosing serious games, teachers also need to consider a number of issues including: socially and developmentally appropriate content; curriculum-alignment; expense and/or licensing issues; the capacity to play the game over short time periods; the suitability of the game for the school's digital platform/s; and the likelihood of high levels of student engagement (Ulicsak Williamson, 2010).

3.2.2. Lack of gadgets and devices—In today's teachers' activities, gadgets and other electronic devices are widely used in the country. These devices are needed in the delivery of lessons and most of the time, the budget in purchasing such devices came from the teachers' own pocket in order to provide what the learners' need in the classroom. Gadgets are one of the fundamental devices that teachers rely on in the present times. Lack of devices inside the classroom creates a barrier to the necessary information the students should have. Some instructional materials needed for the implementation of the game-based education takes time and effort to produce. Recycled materials may be used but some materials must be procured in order to match the requirements of the game. Prior to developing a game-based learning curriculum, it is essential for teachers to be able to evaluate the condition of their learning environment, including the organizational support structure, the availability of hardware and software and any other available assets or obstacles. Albarico et al. (2014) revealed that the inclusion of diverse interests, skills, and maturity levels, as well as interactive learning, helped in aligning the instructional materials with the BSEd-TLE goals. It is also revealed that all TLE program areas have instructional material available and that these materials are used ap-

appropriately in the corresponding courses. But the findings also indicated that there was not enough teaching resources, tools and equipment in relation to the number of students enrolled.

3.2.3. Computer literacy of teachers and students—Educators' competence is required to continue to develop and innovate, not only for conventional learning models but also for online learning. Competence affects learning activities, which use game-based learning. Thus, educators who have useful competence will seriously produce a creative and easy-to-understand learning media to help students face learning challenges (Baumert et al., 2020; Fauth et al., 2019). Using a word processor, email, mailing lists, and the World Wide Web are some of the most fundamental computer literacy abilities. In today's world, computer literacy is even regarded as being as crucial for students in the classroom as writing, reading, and math. Given the increased use of computers for activities in today's educational institutions, these abilities are crucial (Jenkins, 2008). Supporting technology-based learning requires a combination of computer skills, educational competency, and technological expertise. Because online learning presents obstacles under unknown conditions, educational actors are more adaptable to changing circumstances. To ensure that teaching and learning activities operate smoothly and do not diminish the value of learning, the government and educational institutions must collaborate (Wardoyo et al., 2021).

3.2.4. requires extensive planning—As the educational system is being questioned, technology integration is growing. While there were several opportunities to integrate various technologies into classroom training, it is important to know how successful game-based learning is when used in conjunction with traditional classroom instruction. In order to achieve the goal that the teacher has established, classroom instruction is essential. Students' assessment results will be significantly impacted when in-

struction is inadequate. Traditional games are usually utilized for game-based learning implementation in the Philippine education, while the uncontrolled booming of internet games is less known. This has been supported by learning principles that emphasize critical and active learning, individualized and contextual learning, and transfer of learning through problem-solving methods (Alviz, 2018). Teachers take on many important roles as they integrate and use games in the classroom (Marklund Taylor, 2014). It also became evident that the skill sets needed to do these tasks well were quite diverse, including subject matter expertise, game literacy, technology skills, and, of course, a strong pedagogical foundation.

3.2.5. Suitability to the lesson—should first consider the level of the game to fit the needs and level of the students. They should choose the game that fits the purpose and content of the lesson. They should also consider the students' characteristics whether they are young, serious minded, motivated to learn or not. Although games can be fun and exciting, we should not lose sight of the pedagogical values in incorporating games in the lesson. Upon the interview, some of the participants in the study focused their attention on the suitability of the game-based education in the lesson and relayed the following statements: All the informants of the study were united in giving focus to the suitability of game-based education to the lesson. They were all concerned on the games and activities they can use and if it fits to the lesson. This can give the teachers new way of teaching and is more related to the 21st century learners where they were more exposed to the online games and other game-based applications present in their smart phone and personal computers. They were also concerned if there were available games and activities they can use and how they should change or revise it to properly be used in the lesson without additional workload for them.

Fig. 4. The Challenges Encountered by Home Economics Teachers in Utilizing Game-Based Education in Teaching Home Economics

3.3. *Insights Drawn from Home Economics Teacher in Utilizin—Game-based Education in Teaching Home Economics* Based on the accounts of the home economics teachers in utilizing game-based education in teaching home economics, some insights were draw to further improve the utilization of game-based education in home economics.

3.3.1. *Proper selection of games and activities—*Teachers can maximize the benefits of the games as expected on the objective of the lesson, but careful planning and selection must come first before introducing it to the class. If properly selected and revised as per needed in the lesson, teachers will have an ease in the delivery of the lesson. Many educators are look-

ing for new digital resources to help them with their teaching methods. This possibility may inherently appeal to teachers, who are inclined to promote instructional games as a means to leverage their pupils’ digital interests. There has been much speculation on the learning potential in serious games (Gee, 2003). Educationally, the teacher should try to inspire students to study the theories themselves. It should be an interactive conversation between the teacher and the learner (also called Socratic Learning). The instructor’s job is to translate the material to be learnt into a skill level appropriate to the learner’s current state of understanding. Based on the Applied Model Game-Based Learning Instructional Design (GBL ID), Khan et al. (2017,

as cited in Nguyen, 2021) reported that the use of digital-game-based learning can increase student engagement as part of lesson design. That means considering the needs and traits of the students, the goals of the lesson or instruction, what counts as valid evidence for creating instruction to promote student movement towards learning goals, game design, implementation, and assessment, finding that aligns with the needs of the students, organizing and developing technical support, and introducing the game in an environment that's similar to the environment where the game will be played by students.

3.3.2. Willingness to learn new skills—Part of the teachers' responsibility as a professional teacher is to acquire new and updated knowledge especially if the students will benefit from it. Teachers' skills and aptitude in computer literacy will greatly help in clerical works and lesson delivery. All these participants were aware that being a schoolteacher is a profession that needs continuous learning, especially with fast-moving technologies in order to cope with the young generation in the 21st century learners. They all agree that learning new skills and concepts is a great opportunity to face the new level of teaching in this era. The teacher's ability to prepare learning goals and deliver lessons has been influenced by training and seminar courses. According to the argument, many classrooms could substantially profit from the intensity level of teaching with the halt of electricity used for teaching and learning. The literature also supports that "Effective professional development is needed in order to use the technology effectively in the classroom (NCLB, 2001). Based on a case study conducted by Issham Ismail (2011) which reveals that Malaysian teachers' responses on their willingness to undergo

training and courses related to the integration of technology in the classroom. All interview responses overwhelmingly agreed that requisite training and courses on the technology will be taken to expand their knowledge.

3.3.3. Readily available gadgets and devices—Devices such as laptop or a television is a vital part in the delivery of game-based education. The students can readily navigate the available devices and can access to the lesson and especially they can also interact to the games presented in the lesson. They can easily participate and engage in the lesson since they can handle and manipulate the device themselves. The teachers are hopeful for their experiences when they are utilizing the game-based education in their lesson. Against all the challenges of limited source of learning materials, teachers were satisfied with their experience through the exciting and new way of delivering the lesson to the students. They realized that with the help and assistance of the school administration and other stakeholders, these challenges will be given an answer. In choosing serious games, teachers also need to consider a number of issues including: socially and developmentally appropriate content; curriculum-alignment; expense and/or licensing issues; the capacity to play the game over short time periods; the suitability of the game for the school's digital platform/s; and the likelihood of high levels of student engagement (Ulcsak Williamson, 2010). The efficiency of educational games rises through pedagogical assistance according to studies by Bober (2010) and Wouters et al. (2013). The authors state that teachers still need to use their professional skills when choosing serious games yet provide a guide of basic evaluation questions for serious games in education.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This section provides an overview of the results from which I drew the implications and future directions from the study. Research Background The purpose of my study was to explore the

Fig. 5. The Insights Drawn from the Experiences and Challenges of Teachers in Utilizing Game-Based Education in Teaching Home Economics

experiences of game-based learning in the home economics of instructors working within the large schools of Tagum City, Davao del Norte. The prior studies showed the facts of experiences as home economics teachers were using game-based learning for their teaching improvement. It also showed the challenges the teachers faced in implementing the program in practice. As they watched the pros and cons of game-based learning, they also offered tips.

4.1. Findings—In order to achieve the research objectives, I applied qualitative phenomenological method with thematic analysis according to the recommendations of Creswell (2006), which employed semi-structured interview questions to provide an authentic understanding of the individuals' lived experiences. In this way, I was able to ask my participants to articulate or make sense of the phenomenon being studied—that being, a phenomenon that the world over needed a lot of in statements that they are using game-based education as a tool to support the teaching of home economics—and use this interviewing method to form your own meanings around the problem in question. The 70 participants were anonymized in this study as their responses and information were kept confidential.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The experiences of the home economics teachers as they utilized game-based education in teaching, one of these themes was the active participation and engagement of the students. Maximum engagement was observed inside the classroom, and it focuses on a learner-centered discussion. Game-based education supported the lesson well and employing a more creative and innovative way of teaching. A clear and precise instruction must be given before the game to be introduced in the lesson thus giving the teachers to create a higher level of activities. Careful planning of the lesson and identifying the interest of the target students became the foundation in crafting the lesson. The second theme in this aspect was the application of technical skills in the delivery of the lesson. The teachers applied their ideas and knowledge in

the implementation of the lesson in game-based education. Teachers need to update and upscale their knowledge in order to level-up their stock knowledge to the new knowledge. Basic knowledge of game-based education is a must have idea before implementing this kind of education. Teachers need to review the skills they already have and assess what they still needed in order to be competent in addressing game-based education. Teachers must possess these skills in order to successfully implement the lesson. The improvement of the course delivery was the third theme that was drawn from the experiences of the home economics teachers in using game-based learning. Using games to help pupils get better at making decisions about when to respond in key moments. It also promotes class participation, teamwork and active participation. Wild Animals game, students can learn and have fun at the same time while learning at the same time. The fourth topic that was identified, based on the instructors' experiences, was that it fit together with their pedagogical styles. This also helps as the professors would need to guide and assist the students during the process, leading to constant positive exchanges. The students used higher level thinking skills to gain the premise of the lesson. Students (and obviously, continue to strive for body condition!) need to read and assess the situation that the lecturers provide. It makes pupils excited; it stimulates quick thinking while solving fun problems. It is teachers with proficiency in information technology who can create environments conducive to the lesson. And then it includes going online to get information about anything that was required in the class. Through the experiences of the home economics teacher using game-based learning,

at least five themes developed. One of these problems was finding appropriate games and activities. The effectiveness of the lesson is largely due to the teachers' game-based learning selection and preparation. This means structuring the activity and allowing students an opportunity to practice the skills that they will need to successfully complete the activity. Another reason why knowledge and perception of different games needs to be considered that in order to tailor learn through play activities according to the abilities of the students. Choosing games and activities that are easy for teachers and students to access and to understand is crucial. This also identifies the material that the instructor should be introducing to the class as well as the relevance of the games and activities involved in the lesson. The second theme identified from the challenges encountered by the home economics teachers as they utilized game-based education in teaching was the lack of gadgets and devices. These devices are needed in the delivery of lessons and most of the time, the budget in purchasing such devices came from the teachers' own pocket in order to provide the learners' need in the classroom. Gadgets are one of the fundamental devices we rely on in the present times. Lack of devices inside the classroom creates a barrier to the necessary information the students should have. It hinders the opportunity of the students to acquire new information and access on the internet the new and updated data needed to accomplish the task or activities. Teachers need to be able to review the condition of their educational environment and that involves the organizational support structure, availability of hardware and software, and the availability of other resources or obstacles, need to be considered before game-based education takes place. The third theme identified from the challenges of the teachers was the computer literacy of teachers and learners. The competence of the teacher and students greatly affects the learning process. Thus, educators who have

useful competence will seriously produce a creative and easy-to-understand learning media to help students face learning challenges. Teachers and students need enough time for the orientation and familiarization of the game and the technology used in game-based education needs to be reviewed. These skills are essential as more tasks and activities are completed using computer technologies. The fourth theme identified was it needs a lot of time in the preparation. The advance preparation and taking time to plan it makes the teachers handle it difficultly. Teachers need to set the lesson plan that the game-based activities can be used and adopted to it. The most common challenge that takes time on the part of instruction and some revision on the features of the game. The last or the fifth theme as identified in the challenges encountered by the home economics teachers was on the suitability of the games to the lesson. Teachers should first consider the level of the game to fit the needs and level of the students. They should choose the game that fits the purpose and content of the lesson. They should also consider the students' characteristics whether they are young, serious minded, motivated to learn or not. Although games can be fun and exciting, we should not lose sight of the pedagogical values in incorporating games in the lesson. They were all concerned about the games and activities they can use and if they fit the lesson. They were also concerned about if there were available games and activities they could use and how they should change or revise it to properly be used in the lesson without additional workload for them. On the insights drawn from the storylines of the participants, there were three themes identified. One was on the proper selection of games and activities to be incorporated in the lesson. Teachers can maximize the benefits of the games, 74 but careful planning and selection must come first before introducing it to the class. If properly selected and revised as per needed in the lesson,

teachers will have and ease in the delivery of the lesson. There is a need to properly select games and activities in utilizing game-based education in teaching. Careful selection and identification of appropriate games before incorporating it to the lesson is a must in order to arrive at the desired outcome of the lesson. The second theme on the insights of the teachers was on the willingness of the teachers to learn new skills. One of the teachers' responsibilities as a professional teacher is to acquire new and updated knowledge especially if the students will be benefited from it. Teachers' skills and aptitude in computer literacy will greatly help in clerical works and lesson delivery. Teaching is a profession that needs continuous learning especially with the fast-moving technologies in order to cope with the young generation in the 21st century. Learning new skills and concept is a great opportunity for teacher to face the new level of teaching in the present times. The third and the last theme in this area is on the readily available gadgets and devices in school and classroom. Teachers' devices such as laptop or a television is a vital part in the delivery of game-based education. The students can readily navigate the available devices and can access to the lesson and especially they can also interact to the games presented in the lesson. They can easily participate and engage in the lesson since they can handle and manipulate the device themselves. Despite the problem in availability of learning resources, they found a great, fun and exciting way of teaching where students are motivated to participate and engage in the lesson.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the findings are properly relayed and used by the significant people whom this research was intended for. Findings of the study were about the active participation and engagement of the students in the lesson discussion, teachers apply their technical skills during the process, the delivery of the les-

son was enhanced, and it supported the teaching style of the facilitators. Other findings from the study were the challenges encountered by the teachers in utilizing game-based education was on the difficulty in finding appropriate games and activities to incorporate in the lesson, lacking gadgets and devices to use, the computer literacy of teachers and students, it needs a lot of preparation and the suitability of games in the lesson. Lastly, the insight drawn from the study were on the proper selection of games and activities, willingness of teachers to learn new skills and the readily available gadget and devices. The whole process cannot be done by one indicator only, this involves the active participation the teacher as facilitator and the students that will be engaged in the process. Application of the skills learned through the updating of knowledge of the teachers were a great help in the improvement of the teaching and learning process. This study gives an opportunity to incorporate some comments and suggestions and findings for the improvement of the home economics learning resources such as computer laboratory and classroom devices as used by the teacher and students through the following entities: 76 The division where the school belongs may give their support in providing necessary training and seminars for the teachers, gadgets and devices both for the teachers and students to prepare the school in the technological development. Collaboration and open communication with the needs of the school must be relayed and delivered for the improvement of the school facilities and classroom structures. With the continuous technological upgrade of the Department of Education, this may be one of the factors that may help in the improvement of the teaching and learning process. The school heads may establish stronger ties with the local community leaders and private sectors for the adaptation of the program for the benefit of the students. School heads and the adopt a school program coordinator may reach out the

private sectors for the needed help in the said proposal. Careful planning with the local leaders will lay down significant plan of actions for the future and cater the needs of the students. The home economics teachers to be always willing to learn and help develop a more interactive and exciting lesson as possible. The teachers along with the key personalities in the school and community may undergo additional trainings game-based education. The teachers may also conduct overall assessment of the capacity of the home economics laboratory, computer laboratory and other learning resources. The stakeholders to be more actively engaged and help in assisting the teachers and students in every activity they will have. This will also promote the active participation and involvement of other stakeholders concerning the vital needs of the students inside the school and classroom. For the future researchers, a similar study may be conducted in other regions or divisions. The researchers may consider other stakeholders as participants. Studies on game-based education as a support tool of home economics teachers may also be one of the aspects for future research to include support tool and its help in developing the proficiency level of the teachers.

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